

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NLFL)

Board:

Chair: Ronald Visser

Secretary: Jitte Waagen

Treasurer: Erwin Meylemans

Member: Devi Taelmans

During the annual CAA meeting in Siena many people from the CAA-NLFL chapter were present and contributed with various papers.

22-23 October 2015 we held our yearly meeting. Nearly 50 people participated and enjoyed 15 presentations. The subjects we dealt with were the city in 3D, digital archaeology versus the social sciences and daily application of digital tools in archaeology. The presentations were generally good and gave a good overview of the current status of digital archaeology in the Dutch speaking countries. The presentations were given by Bachelor students and people much further in their career, ensuring a good mix of people.

During the meeting we voted on a small change of our constitution to enable a temporary expansion of the board. The change involves that a fourth person can be part of the board for a year. The goal is to ensure continuity and enable a leaving board member to transfer all responsibilities flawlessly. After the year the new member stays in the board and a current member leaves. In this case Erwin will leave the board after the meeting in 2016 and Devi take his place.

Our yearly meeting has cost €980. The paying participants have paid a total of €800. The loss of €180 was generously covered by UvA-ACASA, leading to a balance of €0.

Our next meeting will be a joint meeting with CAA-DE. It will take place in Ghent (B) on the 24th and 25th of November 2016.